

CONSANGUINITY IN INDIA: ITS IMPACT ON HEALTH- A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Consanguineous marriage is a common and preferable custom of marriage in some states of India. Consanguineous marriage may cause transfer of two recessive defective alleles, one from the mother and the other from the father, to off springs; which may cause appearance of congenital anomalies. It is estimated that one billion of the current global population live in communities with a preference for consanguineous marriage. The actual reasons given for the preference of consanguineous marriages are primarily social. In communities with high consanguinity rates, sociological studies indicate that consanguineous marriage could enforce the couples' stability due to higher compatibility between husband and wife who share the same social relationships after marriage as before marriage, as well as the compatibility between the couple and other family members. Multiple studies have established consanguinity as a high cause for birth defects and abnormalities. A risk of autosomal recessive disorders increases in off springs coming from consanguineous marriages due to the increased likelihood of receiving recessive genes from cognate parents. According to population-based case-control studies, a higher risk of stillbirth, decreased cognitive abilities in children are associated with consanguineous marriages. Chances of postnatal mortality are higher in offspring. with the exception of Kerala there is little evidence of a recent overall decline in the prevalence of consanguineous marriage in South India. It is, however, probable that increased urbanization and the gradual shift to smaller family sizes will impose constraints on consanguineous marriage in future generations.

KEYWORDS: Consanguineous marriage, endogamy, homozygosity, recessive disorders, India.

INTRODUCTION

Consanguinity is a term that is derived from two Latin words "*con*" meaning common, or of the same and "*sanguineus*" meaning blood, hence, referring to a relationship between two people who share a common ancestor or blood. In other words, consanguineous marriage refers to unions contracted between biologically-related individuals. In clinical genetics, a consanguineous marriage means union between couples who are related as second cousins or closer.

Global scenario

Consanguineous marriage is most common in the Middle East, West Asia and North Africa and south India. Rate of consanguineous marriage in different countries are dependent on different factors like education level, religion, local tradition, and socio-economic status. Consanguineous marriage is traditional and respected in most communities of North Africa, Middle East and West Asia, where intra-familial unions collectively account for 20–50+% of all marriages. Consanguineous marriages are also practiced among emigrant communities from highly consanguineous countries and regions, such as Pakistan, Turkey, North Africa and Lebanon, now resident in Europe, North America and Australia.

- Less than 1%: United States, Russia, Australia, parts of Latin America and Europe
- 1-10%: China, Latin America, North India, Japan, South Europe and Canada
- 10-50+%: Arab countries, Turkey, Iran, Pakistan, Afghanistan, South India.

Consanguinity in India

The population of India is unique in its size and in the level of sub-division, with 15 major languages and six main religions. The profound influence of caste endogamy has been confirmed by genomic analysis of modern Indian populations which has confirmed the

continuing high level of gene differentiation, with marked divisions according to caste rank. While caste endogamy is universal, India is sub-divided into two major regions with respect to a preference for, or avoidance of, consanguineous marriage. The mainly Indo-European speaking Hindu peoples in the northern states avoid marital unions between biological kin, because of a prohibition on consanguineous marriage believed to date back to approximately 200 BC. By comparison, there is a long tradition of uncle-niece marriage and unions between a man and his maternal uncle's daughter (mother's brother's daughter) in South India.

Consanguineous marriage is common in all Indian Muslim communities. Variations are, however, seen in the levels of consanguineous unions contracted in different branches of Islam and between specific communities, and these differences emphasize the important influence of local and regional customs in the arrangement of marriage contracts. National Family Health Survey (NFHS) surveys the highest rates of consanguineous marriage were reported in Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Why are consanguineous marriages culturally favoured?

The actual reasons for the preference of consanguineous marriages are primarily social. In communities with high consanguinity rates, sociological studies indicate that consanguineous marriage could enforce the couples' stability due to higher compatibility between husband and wife who share the same social relationships after marriage as before marriage, as well as the compatibility between the couple and other family members.

Consanguineous marriage may be more favourable for the women's status, including the wife's better relationship with her in-laws who could support her in time of need. There is a general belief that marrying within the family reduces the possibilities of hidden uncertainties in health and financial issues. It is believed that consanguinity strengthens family ties and enforces family solidarity, with cousin marriage providing excellent opportunities for the transmission of cultural values and cultural continuity. Premarital negotiations regarding financial matters of marriage are more easily conducted and sometimes less costly. Wife's parents prefer to have their daughter living near them and to

enjoy the presence of their grandchildren. Moreover, wealthy landlords may prefer to keep their property within the family.

Impact of consanguinity on different health parameters

Consanguinity increases postnatal morbidity and mortality; recessive genetic disorders will progressively gain greater prominence in the overall spectrum of ill-health.

Reproductive health

Many studies on consanguineous marriages reported earlier parental age at marriage, younger maternal age at first live birth, higher number of infants born to consanguineous parents, similar rates of abortions, and higher rates of still births, postnatal mortality and birth defects in offspring of consanguineous parents. The increased postnatal mortality among the offspring of consanguineous parents may be related to the action of deleterious recessive genes and multi-gene complexes inherited from a common ancestor.

Congenital malformations

Frequency of congenital malformations among newborns of consanguineous unions is about two times the frequency among the general population. Consanguinity rates were noted to be higher among parents of newborns with congenital hydrocephalus and neural tube defects than in the general population in some studies, but not in others. A positive association of consanguinity with cleft lip and/or palate was also reported. Death within first month of birth is mostly because of malformation of gastro-intestinal system of newborn.

Genetic diseases

Consanguinity increases the risk of expression of autosomal recessive conditions in the offspring. This effect is more pronounced for rare disorders. The main impact of consanguineous marriage is an elevation in the rate for homozygotes in recessive disorders. If a new mutation is inserted in such a population, it will spread rapidly and lead to an elevation in carriers' prevalence and an increased number of affected homozygous individuals. Studies from India (South India), where for more than 2,000 years inbreeding is practiced, show no appreciable elimination of recessive lethal and sublethal genes from the

gene pool. Some of inherited genetic disorders are transferred as autosomal recessive in carrier individuals and consanguinity facilitates homozygosity mapping of these genetic disease; which appears in their offspring as congenital anomalies. Congenital anomalies (CA) are the structural or functional anomalies (including metabolic disorders); which are present during birth of the child. These abnormalities can be isolated or seen as part of a syndrome; which results morbidity and mortality of neonates and infants. Based on the WHO (world Health Organization) report, 3% of newborns are associated with CA equals to approximately 3 million fetuses and infants per year. CAs vary from country to country; with lowest rate in Japan (1.07%) and highest rate in Taiwan (4.3%). Social, racial, ecological, and economical issues may have a role in the rate variation.

Disabilities and chronic adult non communicable diseases

Off springs of consanguineous parents are over represented among those with mental retardation, blindness and deaf-mutism. The off springs of consanguineous parents are at a risk of a host of diseases like cancer, mental disorders, hypertension, hearing deficit, diabetes mellitus, epilepsy, asthma, leukemia, beta thalassemia, congenital and non-congenital heart diseases.

Premarital and preconception counselling for consanguinity

Premarital and preconception counselling is one of the most important services to prevent negative health impact in consanguineous populations. Carrier detection and genetic counseling programs have been very successful in reducing the birth prevalence of inherited disorders. premarital screening to identify carrier status and the provision of appropriate counseling has tremendous potential to prevent inherited disease. In offering preconception counseling for consanguinity, it is crucial to distinguish between families with a known genetic or inherited disorder and those with no known such disorder by taking a detailed family history and constructing a four-generation pedigree (including offspring, siblings, parents, grandparents, aunts, uncles, nieces, nephews and first cousins of the consultand or proband). Reports have shown that in certain clinical settings, practice guidelines regarding collecting information on consanguinity as part of family history are not available, despite the relevance of such history in identifying at-risk pregnancies. Specific

questions addressed to the couple could help in eliciting the presence of a genetic or hereditary disorder in the extended family. These could include inquiry about the presence of any of the following in blood relatives:

- Birth defects or congenital anomalies;
- Early hearing impairment;
- Early vision impairment;
- Mental retardation or learning disability;
- Developmental delay or failure to thrive;
- Inherited blood disorder;
- Unexplained neonatal or infant death in offspring;
- Epilepsy; and
- Undiagnosed severe condition.

In families with hearing, vision or mental disabilities, informative family history coupled by clinical data and investigations could differentiate cases that are associated with consanguinity from cases caused by other factors.

If family history points to the presence of a genetic disorder, then primary health care providers could refer the couple to a specialized genetic counseling clinic. This helps in estimating the precise risks to the offspring and in diagnosing their carrier status for autosomal recessive disorders known to be present in the family whenever such tests are feasible and applicable. If they have a genetic disorder in their family, a stepwise procedure is attempted starting with construction of a pedigree and taking a detailed family history.

CONCLUSION

Consanguinity is a deeply rooted social trend. The rising public awareness on possible preventive measures for congenital disorders has led to an augmentation in the number of couples seeking preconception and premarital counseling on consanguinity. In both high and low income countries, there is a capacity to provide health education for consanguinity at individual, family and community levels delivered by primary health care personnel with preconception and premarital genetic counseling, and diagnosis. Rather than

discouraging consanguineous marriages in populations with long-held such tradition, ensuring access to preconception and premarital counseling services is the logical way to proceed and more likely both to receive community acceptance and be successful in maintaining and improving health. Increasing public literacy on consanguinity could be achieved by providing proper education and training to primary health care workers on all health and social issues related to consanguinity. with the exception of Kerala there is little evidence of a recent overall decline in the prevalence of consanguineous marriage in South India. It is, however, probable that increased urbanization and the gradual shift to smaller family sizes will impose constraints on consanguineous marriage in future generations. Although consanguineous marriage may remain culturally desirable, a major shift in the balance between the social and economic benefits associated with intra-familial marriage and adverse health outcomes can be predicted. These changes are already underway in India and new diagnostic, counselling and treatment skills are urgently needed, alongside appropriate community education programmes. Since genetic disease already presents as a major national problem, it would be appropriate if programmes to determine the most prevalent genetic diseases in different parts of the country and in different sub-communities were initiated without delay.

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